

“ WHAT IS THE PRONOUN AND HOW CAN WE USE IT?”

Termiz state pedagogical institute Department of foreign language
and literature 1-coure 103-group

Yusupov Asadbek G'afurovich

Annotation: This article discusses the pronoun,its types,and its correct use in the sentence.This cases of the pronoun are clearly explained in English.

Key words: pronouns,personal pronouns,demonstrative pronouns,interrogative pronouns,relative pronouns,indefinite pronouns,reciprocal pronouns,dummy(expletives)pronouns.

What is a pronoun?

A pronoun is a word that stands in for a noun,often to avoid the need to repeat the same noun over and over.

Like nouns, pronouns can refer to people,things,concepts and places.Most sentences contain at least one noun and pronoun.

People tend to use "pronouns" to mean personal pronouns specifically,but there are many other kinds of pronouns that are just as important to English grammar.

e.g: I asked her if the headphones were hers, but she said they belonged to someone else.

Which of them do you prefer? Help yourself to whichever you like.

How are pronouns used in sentences?

The main function of pronouns is to replace nouns.Because of this,they are used in sentences in similar ways to nouns.Like nouns,pronouns commonly serve as the subject of a sentence,followed by a verb.

Examples: Pronouns as subject:

I like to play chess.

We have never been to Germany before.

1. Personal pronouns(first-, second-,and third-person):

Personal pronouns are words like "he" that refer to yourself,the person you are addressing,or other people and things.They usually refer to an an antecedent but may occur without one when the reference is self-evident (e.g: "I" always refers to the person saying or writing it)

Personal pronouns can change their form based on:

- Person (first-,second-,or third-person)
- Number (singular or plural)
- Gender (masculine,feminine,neuter,or epicene)
- Case (subject,object,possessive,or reflexive)

The impersonal pronoun "one" is used in general statements about no particular person.It has fewer forms than the personal pronouns but is otherwise used in the same way.

Person	Number (& gender)	Subject	Object	Possessive	Reflexive	
First	Singular	I	me	mine	myself	
	Plural	we	us	ours	ourselves	
Second	Singular	you		yours	yourself	
	Plural	you		yours	yourselves	
Third	Masculine singular	he	him	his	himself	
	Feminine singular	she	her	hers	herself	
	Neuter / inanimate singular	it		its	itself	
	Gender-neutral singular (epicene)	they		them	theirs	themselves
	Plural	they		them	theirs	themselves
Impersonal	—	one	—	—	oneself	

2. Demonstrative pronouns:

The four demonstrative pronouns(this,that,these and those) are used to indicate something previously mentioned or in conversation,something that is clear from the context.For example,in the sentence "Take this","this" has no explicit antecedent,but it would be clear in context that it referred to whatever object you were being given.

The demonstrative pronoun give information about the relative closeness (literal or figurative) of the things they refer to, especially when they they're contrasted with each other:

- The "near" demonstrative this(singular) or these(plural) indicates something close to you.

- The "far" demonstrative that(singular) or those(plural) indicates something farther from you.

e.g: This is an apple, and those are oranges.

3. Interrogative pronouns:

Interrogative pronouns are used (along with other types of interrogative words) to introduce questions. The interrogative pronouns are:

- What and which, used to ask questions about things.
- Who and whom, used to ask about people.
- Whose, used to ask about ownership.

e.g: Whose is this jacket?

What were your favourite classes at school?

4. Relative pronouns:

A relative pronoun is used to introduce a relative clause—a phrase that usually supplies more information about the preceding noun. They have a lot in common with interrogative pronouns. The relative pronouns are:

- Which(ever), that, and what(ever), used in relation to things.
- Who(ever) and whom(ever), used in relation to people.
- Whose, used to indicate ownership.

e.g: The first thing that I thought of was cloud.

It doesn't matter whose it was, it's ours now!

Whoever broke the chair should own up to it.

5. Indefinite pronouns:

Indefinite pronouns are words like "somebody" that refer to an unspecified person or thing. Many of them are formed using some combination of some-, any-, every-, or no-, with -thing, -one, -where, or -body.

There are also various indefinite pronouns used to describe quantity, such as "little", "many", "none" and "enough". And there are distributive pronouns like "neither" and "each" that allow you to distinguish between options.

The impersonal pronoun "one" can also be regarded as indefinite.

e.g: Try to think of somewhere nice to go for dinner.

No one likes him, and he doesn't like anyone.

Some are born lucky while others have to work hard for everything they get.

6. Reciprocal pronouns:

Reciprocal pronouns are used to indicate a reciprocal relationship between two people or things, where the members of a group each perform the same action relative to the other(s). The English reciprocal pronouns are each other and one another.

e.g: Siblings often compete with each other for parental attention.

It's important that we treat one another with respect.

7. Dummy pronouns (Expletives):

A dummy pronoun (also called an expletive) is a pronoun that doesn't have any explicit meaning but is necessary to the sentence structure. Unlike other pronouns dummy pronouns don't actually replace a noun.

The two words used as dummy pronouns in English are it and there. Note that both words can also fulfill other grammatical roles. Dummy pronouns are commonly used to talk about the weather, to emphasize certain elements in a sentence, or to introduce the existence of something.

e.g: It rained yesterday, but today it's bright and sunny.

There are thousands of different species of birds in the world.

It isn't clear to me what you mean.

	Subject Pronouns	Object Pronouns	Possessive Adjectives	Possessive Pronouns	Reflexive Pronouns
1st person singular	I	Me	My	Mine	Myself
2nd person singular	You	You	Your	Yours	Yourself
3rd person singular (male)	He	Him	His	His	Himself
3rd person singular (female)	She	Her	Her	Hers	Herself
3rd person	It	It	Its	Its	Itself
1st person (plural)	We	Us	Our	Ours	Ourselves
2nd person (plural)	You	You	Your	Yours	Yourselves
3rd person (plural)	They	Them	Their	Theirs	Themselves

In conclusion, the subjects of pronoun in English is very comprehensive. Among other things, this article has briefly discussed the use of pronouns, their types and the order in which they are used in sentences. I believe that this information will serve as a great source of knowledge for everyone.

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